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**THE HISTORY OF THE EMERGENCE OF ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS OF
THE CITY OF SAMARKAND AND THEIR PLACE IN UZBEKISTAN ARCHITECTURE**

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Abstract: In this article, architectural monuments and historical buildings made by historical figures who had a high contribution to the historical development and prosperity of the city of Samarkand are studied and researched based on deep scientific research. Proposals and recommendations for preservation and restoration of these historical monuments have been developed.

Key words. Samarkand city, architectural monuments, Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Gori Amir, Observatory, mausoleum.

Introduction

As a result of the research carried out in the city of Samarkand, in the XIV-XV centuries, Movarounnakh gathered incalculable wealth and countless skilled craftsmen brought from the conquered countries during the Timurid period. Large-scale construction work has begun. It embodies the architectural experience of the peoples of the East.

Only four of the largest architectural monuments of that time have remained. These are the ruins of Aksaray and the Dorussaodat complex in Shahrisabz, the tomb of Temur's generation, the mausoleum of the fanatic-mystic Khwaja Ahmad Yassavi in Turkestan, and the mosque known as Bibikhanim, which is considered huge in the Muslim East in the capital Samarkand.

According to tradition, there was a market near the city gate. In honor of Amir Temur's victorious war against India, a new mosque was built in place of the old mosque. According to folk tales, the Jame Mosque, built by Amir Temur, occupied an entire dahash of the city. Its length is 167 meters and its width is 109 meters, stretching from east to west. On the eastern side of the main part of the building, there was a huge porch and archway, with towers on the sides. A huge piece of the front of the gate, decorated with kungura and bows, was pushed forward. The width of the peshtok is 46 meters, and its height is 36 meters, despite the fact that its upper part has fallen. The upper part of the gate, the northern tower, the arch arch, the upper part of the wall with a marble border at the entrance collapsed due to the earthquake. But the

preserved forms of the ruins of the gate, the colorful glazed ceramics covering its surface leave a strong impression on the person.

There is a gate with a carved marble frame with a door opening from the mesh wall of the peshtok. The year of construction of the mosque and Temur's genealogy are written on the plaque above it. It was damaged due to the collapse of the large gable arch during the earthquake of 1897, and now the remains of the gable can be seen near the small southern mosque.

It is not an exaggeration to say that after Amir Temur, his grandson Mirzo Ulugbek continued the work done for the sustainable development and prosperity of the city of Samarkand.

Literature Review

The main monument of Ulugbek is his famous observatory, which was built at the foot of Kohak (Choponota) hill by the Obirakhmat stream. According to Babur, the observatory was a three-story building, the surface of which was decorated with magnificent tiles.

The main tool of the observatory was a very large angle measuring device (vertical circle), the radius of the circle was 40,212 meters, and the length of the arc was 63 meters. The main instrument was very precisely aligned in the direction of the meridian line from south to north. V. L. Vyatkin says that the structure he found in the trench of the observatory was "nothing but a part of a large quadrant, half of which was below the horizon, and the other half was above it" [1]. The height of the part of the tool preserved in the trench is 10 meters. However, the investigations carried out by Academician T.N. Qoriniyozov and G.D. Jalolov prove that this instrument was not a quadrant, but a sextant.

Academician T.I. Qoriniyozov wrote in his book "Ulugbek's school of astronomy" "This important tool of Ulugbek was used to determine the main fixed elements of astronomy: the inclination of the ecliptic to the equator, the length of the tropical year." This instrument was designed to observe the Sun in general, including the Moon and planets. An arc of 60° was absolutely enough for such observations" [2].

In recent times, the main instrument of the observatory was not a sextant, but a quadrant. This opinion is supported, for example, by Professor N.I. Leonov. The professor said that "the skill of the 15th century Samarkand astronomers, the enormous size of the main instrument and the perfection of its construction ensured that the observation of the Sun, Moon and planets was surprisingly accurate" [3].

It included cities not only in Central Asia, but also in Russia, Armenia, Iran, Iraq and even Spain. Ulugbek's astronomical works were based on the theory of geocentrism (the center of the universe is the Earth). This was natural for the Middle Ages.

I. Yu. Krachkovsky, one of the greatest Soviet orientalists, said that Ulugbek's star tables were "the last achievement of medieval astronomy and the highest peak of the science of astronomy that could be reached before the invention of the telescope". 4].

The achievements of Samarkand astronomers who lived in the 15th century are so important. The results of their scientific achievements had a strong influence on the development of science in the West and the East, including India and China.

According to the description of the famous orientalist, academician V.V. Bartold, who deeply studied the era of the great Uzbek astronomer: "The fifteenth century was a time of struggle between two

worldviews for Central Asia. The representative of one of these worldviews is Temur's grandson Ulugbek, who in the past ruled in Samarkand, Temur's capital" [5].

Methodology

Such research methods as analysis and synthesis of scientific knowledge, systematic approach, comparison, classification, grouping have been widely used in this article.

Analysis and results

Although the large and small mosques differ greatly in size, their composition is the same. Stepped domes rise from the roofs of the small mosque. The big gable is equal to the gable of the gate. The large dome of the mosque (internal diameter 14.6 m.) is covered by a huge ravq and minarets from the front. The exterior of the large mosque, with its gilded, blue ornamentation, is reminiscent of the jagged, tiled ornaments of the small mosque.

The mosque was built very big without taking into account the occurrence of strong earthquakes. Despite the depth of the underground stone foundation, as well as the brick wall made of ganch mixture (about 5 meters thick), during the lifetime of Timur, soil started to pour on people's heads from the cracked dome during prayers. The outer domes of the small mosque were not preserved, the pediment and both domes of the large mosque were destroyed, and the corner minaret and the weak stone column gallery were destroyed by the earthquake.

We had the opportunity to study the wonderful art monument created by the talented architects of the past, carefully preserved by our state. It is protected by our state as a cultural heritage. Bibikhanim mosque is also being renovated.

One of the famous ancient architectural monuments - Gori Amir complex is located in one of the most beautiful places of Samarkand - Okhunboboyev street, which stretches east-south from the University Avenue, where huge maple trees grow.

This complex is named after the Gori Amir mausoleum, the last residence of Amir Temur, who founded a great empire. But the first buildings on the territory of the complex were built at the end of the 14th century and are associated with the name of Temur's great-grandson Muhammad Sultan. According to historical sources, Muhammad Sultan built a madrasa and a house next to the Ruhabad mausoleum (the Ruhabad mausoleum is visible from the north side of Gori Amir).

The facades of madrasahs and houses facing each other protrude into the courtyard. The other two sides of the courtyard are surrounded by high walls. In the middle of each wall, there was a porch leading to different parts of the ensemble.

After the death of Timur, mutual wars for the throne started and prevented the completion of the mausoleum. The country calmed down only in 1409. Temur's son Shahrukh makes Herat the capital. He appoints Ulugbek as the governor of Samarkand. Temur's sons Mironshah za Shahrukh were also buried in the mausoleum. After the death of Ulugbek in 1449, his body was buried in the Gori Amir mausoleum.

According to some information, a madrasa was in operation in the 17th century, and only the ruins of the building of the Khanaqah were preserved. During these times, Temur's name was not mentioned with respect as before. The mausoleum was called Syed Baraka. During the social and economic crisis of the 20s of the 18th century, the Madrasah of Muhammad Sultan, which was destroyed, begins to turn into a ruin.

Since the madrasa and the house of Muhammad Sultan were forgotten, the early researchers of the monuments of Samarkand could not determine the place where the madrasa and the house fell for a long time.

Behind the wall on the eastern side of the courtyard, the remains of the Madrasa of Muhammad Sultan can be seen. During the improvement works on the territory of the monument, several rows of bricks were raised so that the remains of the madrasa could be seen. Now it is clearly visible from the hill. Muhammad Sultan madrasa is the oldest preserved madrasa in Uzbekistan.

The most important part of the complex is the external architecture of the Gori Amir mausoleum. An octagonal prism supporting a cylindrical drum with many ribs and a huge dome forms the basis of the composition of the building volume. The walls of the mausoleum are covered with blue, airy and white glazed tiles, these tiles are cut in a geometric shape, with Arabic lettering and are skillfully made. The architect skillfully decorates large levels of buildings using similar forms.

Great attention was paid to the dome when working on the exterior of the mausoleum. Although the diameter of the lower part of the dome is 15 meters and the height is 12.5 meters, the weight is not noticeable. This is because its dome consists of 64 ribs. The top of the dome is covered with mysterious tiles. In its honor, there are beautiful jimjimas made of such wet tiles. The outer dome of the mausoleum was placed on top of the inner dome to make the external appearance of the monument more beautiful.

Two pieces of jade were among the spoils of Ulugbek's victory over the Mongols in 1425. These two stones were carefully worked, connected to each other, and placed on Temur's grave.

In 1740, during the conquest of the Khanate of Bukhara, Shah Nadirshah of Iran (at that time, Samarkand belonged to the Khanate of Bukhara) ordered the stone on the tomb of Timur to be taken to Mashhad. But Nadirshah, who was afraid of being blasphemed, returned from this intention and after long and difficult journeys for that time, he brought the stone back to its place.

There is a staircase leading down to the arch on the east side of the mausoleum. This staircase leads down to the lower floor of the mausoleum - the shack. The ceiling of the building on the lower floor is slanted in the form of a twelve-sided dome, and the interior decoration is very simple. In the same order as the saganas placed on the Timurids are on the upper floor, here is the same order. Each grave is covered with marble.

The ruins of a huge building stand near the ancient mausoleum and cemetery of Khoja Abdidarun, about half an hour's walk from Registan of Samarkand. This monument is popularly known as Ishratkhana.

Khirot became a great center of all sciences and arts during the reign of Sultan Husayn Boykara, and especially during the reign of Alisher Navoi. During this period, cultural life and activities in Uzbekistan, mainly literature, book sciences and concrete knowledge, were depressed. The wonderful architectural school of Samarkand architects has reached even greater maturity. Although buildings were not built on a large scale as in the previous period, in the second half of the 15th century, the movement of building healthy, luxurious and beautiful buildings increased even more. Office can be a bright example of these.

According to the pictures and photos taken earlier, the office building was irreparably damaged already in the last century: the upper part of the main dome and the roofs of the side buildings collapsed, and most of the tiles fell. In the earthquake of 1903, the dome completely collapsed and the complex

dome-shaped top of the central room was swept away with it. Only ruins remain from the office. Nevertheless, it remains one of the most attractive relics of Timurid Samarkand.

Ishratkhana occupies a special place among the mausoleums not only in Central Asia, but also in the entire Muslim world. Architecturally, it consists of several complex interconnected buildings.

The artistic decoration of the front of the office reflects its general plan. This front (facade) of the office, facing south-west, is distinguished by a dome-shaped gable, which surprises one with its proportions. The base of the peshtok, i.e. the lower part, is divided into arches, and there is a two-story porch on both sides. These main pieces of architecture are accentuated by belt-like borders.

The northeast side of the office is designed differently. There is no pediment here, but it consists of elements of artistic decoration. These elements start from the outer porches and increase towards the central wall arch. Lajovard or blue glaze decorations were used on the seams between individual bricks. The borders in different parts of the building are decorated with the use of round or oval steps with a colorful pattern. In the places very close to the eyes of the building, such as the three-corner shelves of the arches and the places where the inscriptions were written (unfortunately, these inscriptions have fallen and disappeared), the flowery louvre decorations decorated with elegant carvings are given to the decoration.

On the north side of Gori Amir stands another magnificent monument known as Ruhabad. This is the mausoleum of Sheikh Burhoniddin Sagaraji, who died in the 80s of the 14th century. Its entire composition is similar to the constructions of the XI-XII centuries, but with its grandeur and grandeur, it is among the magnificent constructions typical of the Timur period.

The surface of the mausoleum was almost not decorated with lacquer, and it was not even decorated with a luxurious roof. Facades differ from each other only in insignificant details.

Once upon a time, there were three doors to enter the mausoleum. The magnificent carved door on the southern facade was later knocked down, so it can only be seen from inside the mausoleum.

The second door is on the northern facade, and it was also knocked down. The third carved door on the western facade is quite new and was built in the 19th century during the reign of Samarkand Governor Muzaffar Khan.

The internal width and size of the mausoleum is surprising with the quality of its decorations. Poly is made of brick, and several saganas have been preserved. The walls are plastered.

The square part of the building is quite high, and the walls are plastered. In the middle of each is a curved shelf. The wall frame corresponds to the size of the building and is about two meters high. The Izora is covered with a six-sided ceramic coating without a glaze. Lojuvard glaze was used very sparingly in Charabzali.

The dome rests on six arches. Light enters the mausoleum from the windows. Due to the high windows, the dome building is well lit and looks majestic.

The earthquake of 1907 caused great damage to the monument. At that time, the dome was badly damaged and the walls were cracked in several places.

It is said that the mausoleum was buried about one and a half meters due to the layer formed gradually over the course of six hundred years. Now it is cleared from the layer. The interior and dome

of the mausoleum were restored, and the octagonal base was strengthened. General strengthening of the mausoleum is also underway.

In the 15th century, there was a stone road from the mausoleum to Gori Amir. Thanks to the branches of the trees on both sides of the road, it was pleasantly cool even in the heat of summer. In medieval books, this road is known as Shahrokh.

In the 19th century, during the time of Muzaffar Khan, a complex of buildings was erected in front of the mausoleum. Including a mosque, a minaret and a gate house.

The buildings disappeared with the passage of time, and the gatehouse and minaret were preserved a little further south from the mausoleum. The royal white stone road has become a legend. However, the creation of an unknown architect - a wonderful monument of creative folk art - the magnificent Ruhabad has been flowing since the 14th century. The architecture of the mausoleum amazes with its simplicity, clarity, and impressiveness. The decorations given in moderation made this majestic monument even more beautiful.

On the outskirts of the ancient city of Samarkand, on the hill of Kohak, the great scientist of his time, Amir Mirzo Ulugbek, a group of astronomers carefully observed the lights of the sky and those who saw them wrote in the book "Zijn".

A huge observatory building was built on this famous hill in 832 AH (1428-1429) by order of Ulugbek. At that time, such an observatory building did not exist either in the West or in the East. Zahiriddin Babur wrote: "Another high building is located in the Kokhak valley, it is a tool to finish the work. There are three levels. Ulugbek Mirza finished Ziji Kuragoni with this rasad.

Ulugbek attracted prominent astronomers of that time, including the famous mathematician Ghiyosiddin Jamshid and others, to the construction of this wonderful scientific facility. They developed the project of the observatory, improved astronomical instruments. At the end of the 15th century, according to the historian Mirkhond, "... a supreme decree was issued that skilled craftsmen should start the building for the observatory. Maulana Nizamiddin al-Koshiy, who was the guardian of the science of astronomy, the second Ptolemy (Ptolemy), who embodied the catalog of Greek scientists - Maulana Ghiyosiddin Jamshid, who reached the heights of science, took part in this work.

Abdurazzaq Samarkandi, one of the young historians of that time, wrote in his book "Matla us-sa'dayn wa majma ul-bahrayn" ("The twinkling of two blessed (stars) and the joining of two seas"), "Ulugbek was good at his profession." famous mathematicians, geometers, astronomers and builders were surrounded by prominent scientists of that time: Maulana Salahiddin Musa Muhammad Qazizada al-Rumi (the modern Plato), Maulana Ali Kushchi (Batlimus of the era), famous scientists G' Yasiddin al-Khusti and Mu'iniddin were invited to Samarkand."

It would not be right to attribute the construction of an observatory in Samarkand and the creation of astronomical tables to Ulugbek alone. It is known that Central Asia is one of the most ancient centers of world culture, and its peoples have made a worthy contribution to the treasury of human science, literary science, literature and art.

In the 9th-16th centuries, Central Asia was famous for astronomers and mathematicians. Al-Khwarizmi's (780-850) scientific work at the Baghdad Observatory, Al-Biruni's (973-1048) scientific works in the field of astronomy, Abu Ali ibn Sina's (980-1037) contribution to world science, Umar

Khayyam (1040-1123)) scientific activities in Isfahan observatory and Nasriddin Tusi (1201-1271) in Maraga observatory and scientific works of others are extremely important.

Astronomers from Samarkand expanded the ranks of famous Eastern scientists. The observatory was an incomparable example in the history of medieval science in terms of its equipment. The location of the Ulugbek observatory has been unknown for hundreds of years. Only in 1908, Samarkand archaeologist V. L. Vyatkin (1869-1932) managed to find the remains of the ruined observatory based on historical documents. Since then, the archaeological study of this rare astronomical monument has been started.

I. A. Sukharev, professor M.YE during the archaeological investigation of the Ulugbek observatory in the Soviet period. Masson participated, in particular, professor of the Institute of History and Archeology of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan V.A. Shishkin's expedition played an important role.

As a result of a long and careful study of the monument, it was found that the observatory was a large cylindrical building, and he tried to describe its appearance as it was in the time of Ulugbek. The plan of this building is very complex, there are large halls, rooms, corridors.

In 1949, the government of Uzbekistan erected a marble monument on the site of the observatory. In 1964, the memorial museum named after Ulugbek was completed and ceremonially opened.

During the period when Ulugbek lived and worked, important historical events took place. During his 35-year reign, Ulugbek's grandfather, Amir Temur, was able to create a great empire from the Syr Darya and Zarafshan rivers to the Indus and Ganges rivers, from Tien Shan to the Bosphorus. The richest countries of the East, including Iran, and India were shaken under the feet of the terrible Jahangir.

Amir Temur attracted almost half the world. He dreamed of conquering the whole world, saying that "just as God is alone, there should be only one king in the world".

The importance of Samarkand as a center of handicrafts, trade and scientific thinking in the East increased especially during the period of Timur and his successors. Samarkand became one of the scientific centers of world importance in the 15th century - during the reign of Ulugbek.

Ulugbek was the son of Shahrukh and was born on March 22, 1391. As a child, he accompanied his grandfather Temur in his military campaigns.

Amir Temur took great care of the education of his beloved grandson. He entrusted Ulugbek to his elder wife Sarai Mulkhanim. In Temur's last campaign to China, Ulugbek was among his troops and was with his grandfather when he died on February 18, 1405 in the city of Otrar.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is known that Timur built a luxurious building for himself in Shahrisabz, his hometown, and made a marble saghana. After Temur's sudden death, such a political situation arose that his body was buried in a mausoleum built for his grandson in Samarkand. This mausoleum was also built by Temur. That's why the slab with the name of the great Temur was not installed on the stone hut in Shahrisabz.

There is reason to say that Ulugbek, imitating his grandfather, started large-scale construction works for the burial of nobles near the Gori Amir mausoleum. In terms of beauty, the hut in the mausoleum is not inferior to the hut built by Temur in Shahrisabz.

The mausoleum is lit by a latticed window with colored glass. The interior of the mausoleum is brightly lit by the sunlight passing through these windows. The decoration of the mausoleum shows the high art achieved by the masters of the Middle East and is made in accordance with local traditions.

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